

PROGRESS OF REGIONAL RURAL BANKS IN INDIA

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(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:02.01.2024)

MS 3153

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract

The study was undertaken to assess the progress of Regional rural banks in India, results revealed that the performance of Regional Rural Banks in India has drastically improved from the period of its establishment, as steps for their improvement were initiated by the Government of India after the amalgamation process. The minimum recovery percentage was recorded 70.59 per cent in June 2001, and the maximum recovery percentage was recorded 82.51 per cent in June 2016. The highest total funds of RRBs Rs. 99493.00 crores were observed in FY 2020-21 and lowest Rs. 8583.00 crores was observed in FY 2001-02. Therefore, total funds of RRBs in all over India show an increasing trend from 2001-20. From the study we observed that the amount of investment of RRBs increased from Rs. 30531.64 crores in the year 2001-02 to Rs.2,75,658 crores in the year 2020-21 registering the growth of 9.88 per cent. There is no constant improvement can be seen in Return on investment it was 1.97 per cent in 2001-02 and reached to its minimum level of 0.61 per cent in 2020-21.

Keywords: Amalgamation, Investment, Recovery percentage, performance, Return on Investment.

Introduction:

Regional rural Banks plays a significance role in the agriculture and rural developments of India. The RRBS have more reached to the rural area of India, through their huge network. The success of rural credit in India is largely depends on their financial strength.

To provide adequate banking and credit facilities for agricultural and other rural sectors, Regional Rural Banks were founded under the requirements of an ordinance passed on September 26, 1975, and the RRB Act 1976. As a result of the recommendations of the Narasimham Committee on Rural Credit, five RRBs were established on October 2, 1975, during Indira Gandhi's government. The purpose was to include rural areas into the economic mainstream since around 70 per cent of the Indian population was rural.

RRBs were established with the primary goal of achieving rural development through improved finance for the poorer sections of society. The uniqueness of rural credit is that it tries to provide financing and other services to support the development of agriculture and related activities in order to modernise the rural economy. These institutions supplement the existing institutional credit infrastructure while also reducing the involvement of informal credit providers, particularly unethical money lenders.

Regional Rural Banks are required to operate within a specific geographic area for which they have been formed. Typically, each RRB's operating area is limited to a few districts within the state in which it is established. By way of a notification, the federal government, in collaboration with NABARD and the Sponsor Banks, determines the region of operation of RRBs. Because RRBs are also entitled to open branches or appoint agencies within their defined areas, it is required for them to locate their Head Office in the heart of their notified area of operation. The purpose of this research was to look into the progress of RRBs in various Indian states.

Methodology:

The study was based on secondary data collected for 20 years from 2001-02 to 2020-21, various sources using appropriate analytical techniques to satisfy the objective.

Table 1: Branch Expansion and District coverage of RRBs during 2001-2020

Years	No. of RRBs	No. of Districts (Covered)	No. of Branches	Growth percent
2000-01	196	484	14,311	-
2001-02	196	511	14,390	0.55
2002-03	196	516	14,433	0.3
2003-04	196	518	14,445	0.08
2004-05	196	523	14,484	0.27
2005-06	133	525	14,494	0.07
2006-07	96	534	14,520	0.18
2007-08	91	594	14,761	1.66
2008-09	86	616	15,181	2.85

Paired t-test

A paired t-test is a method used to test whether the mean difference between pairs of measurements is zero or not. It is used to assess the progress of RRBs in India.

Formula for paired t-test

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n \sum d^2 - (\sum d)^2}{n-1}}}$$

Where,

$\sum d$ is the sum of differences,

d - difference per paired value and

n - number of samples

When $n_1 = n_2 = n$ and the two samples are not independent but the sample observations are paired together, then Paired t-test test is applied.

Results and Discussion:**1. Branch Expansion Programme/ Banking Solutions**

The table 1 shows clearly that the number of RRBs decreased to 43 in the year 2020-2021 in comparison to 196 in the year 2001-02. It is because of amalgamation that starts in the year 2005 and still in the process. However, on the other side the number of branches and district coverage increased significantly from 14,311 branches covering 511 districts with 196 RRBs in 2001-2002 to 21,856 branches covering 525 districts with 43 RRBs in 2020-2021 recording the growth of 0.02%. The increase in the number of branches over a period is 1.52 times and the district coverage is 1.08 times.

Test "t" was performed to know whether the pre-decade period performance of branches expansion is significantly differing from the post-decade period performance of branches expansion of the RRBs in India. It observed that value of t- statistics was non-significant. It implies that the performance of branch expansion of RRBs was approximately same for pre- decade and post- decade period.

2009-10	82	618	15,480	1.97
2010-11	82	618	16,001	3.37
2011-12	82	620	16,909	5.67
2012-13	64	635	17,861	5.63
2013-14	57	642	19,082	6.84
2014-15	56	644	20,024	4.94
2015-16	56	644	20,904	4.39
2016-17	56	648	21422	2.4
2017-18	56	648	21747	1.52
2018-19	53	685	21871	0.57
2019-20	45	696	21850	0.1
2020-21	43	525	21856	0.02

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

2. Recovery Performance of RRBs in India

Table 2: Recovery Performance of RRBs during 2001-2020 (Rs. In Crore)

Years	Recovery
2001-02	70.59
2002-03	71.52
2003-04	73.52
2004-05	77.67
2005-06	81.34
2006-07	79.8
2007-08	80.49
2008-09	80.81
2009-10	77.85
2010-11	80.09
2011-12	81.18
2012-13	81.60
2013-14	81.20
2014-15	81.90
2015-16	79.49
2016-17	82.51
2017-18	81.51
2018-19	78.00
2019-20	76.88
2020-21	76.95

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

The Table 2 showing that Recovery Performance of RRBs from 2001-2020. The recovery performance was 70.59 in 2001-02 and there was a slight increase up to 2005-06 i.e., 81.34. However, in the year 2006-07 there was a decrease in recovery performance i.e., 79.80. After that again in the year 2007-08, the rise in recovery performance of RRBs was 80.49 to 81.90 in the year 2014, except in 2009-10, which was 77.85. The highest recovery performance 82.51

was observed in the year 2016-17 and lowest 70.59 was observed in 2001-02. In 2020-21 the recovery performance was 76.95. So, the overall recovery performance is varying from year to year this is because farmers are facing lot of problems in crop yields, Price fluctuations for marketing produce, weather impact on crops and more interest on loans etc., so these are the reasons why the recovery performance will be varying.

3. Total funds of RRBs

Table 3: Total funds of RRBs during 2001-2020 (Rs. In Crore)

Year	Total Funds
2001-02	8583.00
2002-03	9465.00
2003-04	10033.00
2004-05	11705.00
2005-06	13949.00
2006-07	17061.77
2007-08	20226.59
2008-09	23644.94
2009-10	31017.22
2010-11	40329.72
2011-12	46750.84
2012-13	57418.00

2013-14	72402.00
2014-15	84506.00
2015-16	75826.00
2016-17	79921.00
2017-18	87300.00
2018-19	82780.00
2019-20	82588.00
2020-21	99493.00

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

4. Growth in Investments

Table 4: Total Investment of RRBs during 2001-2020 (Rs. In Crore)

Year	Total Investment	Increase over Previous Year	per cent Increase over Previous Year
2001-02	30531.64	-	-
2002-03	33062.79	2531.15	8.29
2003-04	36135.16	3072.37	9.29
2004-05	36767.66	632.5	1.75
2005-06	41182.45	4414.79	12.01
2006-07	45666.14	4483.69	10.89
2007-08	48559.54	2893.4	6.34
2008-09	65909.92	17350.38	35.73
2009-10	79379.16	13469.24	20.44
2010-11	86510.44	7131.28	8.98
2011-12	95974.93	9464.49	10.94
2012-13	108548.00	12573.07	13.1
2013-14	139631.00	31083.00	28.64
2014-15	162781.00	23150.00	16.58
2015-16	169592.00	6811.00	4.18
2016-17	210984.00	41392.00	24.4
2017-18	222266.00	11282.00	5.34
2018-19	226172.00	3906.00	1.75
2019-20	250859.00	24687.00	10.91
2020-21	275658.00	24799.00	9.88

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

From Table 4, it was observed that the total investments of RRBs expanded over the period 2001-20 in increasing direction. In pre-decade, the amount of investment of RRBs all over India increased from Rs. 30,531.64 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 86,510.44 crores in 2010-11. Similarly, in post-decade period the amount of investment of RRBs all over India increased from Rs. 95,974.93 crores in 2011-

12 to Rs. 2,75,658.00 crores in 2020-21. The highest total investments of RRBs Rs. 2,75,658 crores was observed in the year 2020-21 and lowest Rs. 30,531.60 crores was observed in 2001-02. So, the overall Figure 5 shows that there is positive growth in total funds.

5. Return on Investment (ROI)

Table 5: Return on Investment of RRBs during 2001-2020 (Rs. In Crore)

Year	Net Profit	Investment	Return on Investment
2001-02	600.62	30,531.64	1.97
2002-03	607.88	33,062.79	1.84
2003-04	519.29	36,135.16	1.44
2004-05	748.11	36,767.66	2.03
2005-06	617.13	41,182.45	1.5
2006-07	625.15	45,666.14	1.37
2007-08	1328.11	48,559.54	2.74
2008-09	1787.64	65,909.92	2.71
2009-10	2509.18	79,379.16	3.16
2010-11	2349.43	86,510.44	2.72
2011-12	1857.28	95,974.93	1.94
2012-13	2272.93	1,08,548.00	2.09
2013-14	2694.00	1,39,631.00	1.93

2014-15	2745.00	1,62,781.00	1.69
2015-16	2018.00	1,69,592.00	1.88
2016-17	2218.00	2,10,984.00	1.05
2017-18	1525.00	2,22,266.00	0.68
2018-19	-652.00	2,26,172.00	-0.29
2019-20	-2204.00	2,50,859.00	-0.87
2020-21	1682.00	2,75,658.00	0.61

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

From the Table 5, it is clear that investments increased from Rs. 30,531.64 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 2,75,658 crores in 2020-21 but no constant improvement can be seen in Return on investment it was 1.97 per cent in 2001-02 and reached to its minimum level of 0.61 per cent in 2020-21. The maximum Return on investment recorded was 3.16 per cent in 2009-10. From the year 2017-18 there was a gradual decrease in return on investment i.e., 0.68 to 0.61 in 2010-21. In the year 2018-19 the amount of Net profit was in negative value i.e., Rs. -652.00 crores. So, the return on investment is also negative value. Similarly, in the year 2019-20 it was observed that the amount of Net profit is very less i.e., Rs. -2,204.00 crores again the return on investment was also very less compared to the previous year i.e., -0.87 and is the minimum value which is observed in the table.

Even though RRBs had a fast progress of the branch network as well as increased in capacity of business, these institutions went through a large problematic evolutionary progression by reason of the various difficulties like limited area of operations; perception of public is that RRBs are poor people's banks, high risk by reason of expose to the limited target group, problem of government subsidy structures as well as insufficient information of customers leading to low quality assets, shift over to narrow investment banking as a turn-over policy, shortage of skills in treasury management for profit alignment, unionized staff with low commitment to profit orientation then functional effectiveness, serious discouragement of the Board by forces to look up to sponsor banks, GOI, NABARD besides RBI for most decisions and insufficient exertion to attain anticipated levels of excellence in staff capability for managing the affairs as well as business as an independent entity.

Conclusion:

Progress of Regional Rural Banks in India

The following conclusions were emerged from the present study:

1. It was observed from the study that the number of RRBs constantly declining from 196 in FY 2001-02 to 43 in FY 2020-21 indicating the negative growth. This was due to merging of RRBs.
2. The expansion of number of branches showed positive growth trend during period 2001-20.
3. The minimum recovery percentage was recorded 70.59 per cent in June 2001, and the maximum recovery percentage was recorded 82.51 per cent in June 2016.
4. The highest total funds of RRBs Rs. 99,493.00 crores were observed in FY 2020-21 and lowest Rs. 8,583.00 crores were observed in FY 2001-02. Therefore, total funds of RRBs in all over India shows an increasing trend from 2001-20.
5. From the study, it was observed that the amount of investment of RRBs increased from Rs. 30,531.64 crores in the year 2001-02 to Rs. 2,75,658 crores in the year 2020-21 registering the growth of 9.88 per cent.
6. No constant improvement could be seen in Return on investment it was 1.97 21.

Policy Implications

The following are some suggestions for policymakers of the banking sector for further decision-making process.

1. Government should encourage and support banks to take appropriate steps in rural development.
2. Policy should be made by government for opening more branches in weaker and remote areas of state.

References:

1. **Amar Pal Singh¹, K.K. Singh², Anand Singh³, Srishti Kushwah⁴, A.K. Sahi⁵, R.A. Singh⁶, P.K. Singh⁷ Himanshu Singh⁸, 2,018**, Economic Study On Potato Cultivation In Barabanki District Of Uttar Pradesh, Vol. Viii, Issue Special ,August 2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 21-23.
2. **Bagechi Kanak Kanti and Abdul Hadi. (2007)**. Financial Viability and Profitability Trends of Regional Rural Banks in India and West Bengal. *A Comparative Study Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*. 62(3), 373-380.
3. **Devi Sabitha, N. (2016)**. Problems and Prospects of Regional Rural Banks in India. *International Journal of Management Studies and Research, (IJMSR)*. 2(3), 2359-0330.
4. **Ganvir, B.N. (2004)**. Study of Progress and Performance of Regional Rural Banks in India. Unpublished M.SC thesis submitted to: Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri.
5. **Satish Kumar, Vibhor Goyal, Poonam Sharma. (2017)**. Performance Evaluation of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in India. *International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering*. 7 (4), 2249-0558.
6. **Sorokhaibam Somina Devi¹, Sanjay Kumar² and G. D. Rede¹, 2018**, Growth Of Self Help Group-Bank Linkage Programme In India, Vol. Viii, Issue Xxv, April 2018 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, pp 113-118.
7. **Sura and Jasvir, S. (2006)**. Efficacy of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in India: A Conventional Analysis. *The Journal of Indian Management and Strategy*, 11 (4), 4- 12.
8. **Versha Mohindra and Kaur Gian. (2012)**. Total factor productivity of Regional Rural Banks in India: A Malmquist approach. *Economic Affairs*. 56(2), 187- 196.